

RESTRICTIONS ON FREEDOM OF SPEECH TO ENSURE PUBLIC ORDER

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Abstract: The article delves into the intricate balance between upholding freedom of speech and maintaining public order. While freedom of expression is a fundamental human right enshrined in the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the European Convention on Human Rights, it is not absolute. The author explores Article 19 of the ICCPR, which allows for restrictions on freedom of speech under specific conditions. The article analyzes landmark cases from the European Court of Human Rights that illustrate the Court's approach to differentiating permissible restrictions based on the nature and impact of the speech. It further examines the challenges posed by modern communication technologies, particularly the Internet, in regulating harmful content while avoiding undue censorship. The study underscores the necessity for a clear legal framework, legitimate aims, and proportionality in any restriction on freedom of speech, highlighting the role of social media companies in mitigating the spread of harmful information without stifling free expression.

Keywords: freedom of speech, public order, International covenant on civil and political rights, European convention on human rights, European court of human rights, hate speech, incitement to violence, extremist propaganda, legal framework, proportionality, social media regulation, fake news, democratic society.

Freedom of speech, being a basic human right, however, is not absolute. The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights¹ further elaborates on the protection of freedom of expression in Article 19. It states that everyone shall have the right to freedom of expression; this right shall include freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas of all kinds, regardless of frontiers, either orally, in writing or in print, in the form of art, or through any other media of his choice.

In addition to establishing the right in question, this article also creates certain obligations and special responsibilities. From the meaning of article 19², paragraph 3, there arises the right of States to impose restrictions which must be

¹The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (General Assembly resolution 2200A (XXI))

URL: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-covenant-civil-and-political-rights>

²The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (General Assembly resolution 2200A (XXI))

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established by law and in accordance with the principle of necessity, which implies two ideas:

1. For respect of the rights or reputations of others;
2. For the protection of national security or of public order (ordre public), or of public health or morals.

The European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms does not define what constitutes public order, leaving it to member states to define the scope of this concept in their national laws. In practice, the notion of public order has been used to justify restrictions on freedom of expression in a variety of situations, such as in the context of hate speech, incitement to violence or dissemination of extremist propaganda.

The European Court of Human Rights has considered numerous cases concerning restrictions on freedom of expression and the protection of public order. In its jurisprudence, the Court distinguishes between different types of speech and the extent to which they are restricted.

To provide a unified framework for the United Nations to address the issue globally, the UN Strategy and Plan of Action on Hate Speech defines hate speech as...«any kind of communication in speech, writing or behaviour, that attacks or uses pejorative or discriminatory language with reference to a person or a group on the basis of who they are, in other words, based on their religion, ethnicity, nationality, race, colour, descent, gender or other identity factor»³.

For example, in the case of *Jersild v. Denmark*⁴, the ECtHR held that the Danish authorities had violated the applicant's right to freedom of expression by convicting him of aiding and abetting the dissemination of racist ideas. The Court held that the Danish authorities had failed to prove that the applicant's speech posed a real threat to public order or that his statements incited violence.

In contrast, in *Erbakan v. Turkey*⁵, the ECtHR upheld the conviction of a political leader for statements that were considered offensive to Jews and promoting hatred against them. The Court found that such statements were likely to inflame tensions, incite violence and undermine the democratic values of Turkish society.

Incitement to violence is another type of speech that may be restricted under the public order defense. Incitement to violence falls outside the protection conferred by Article 10 where there is an intentional and direct use of wording to

³ What is hate speech? - URL: <https://www.un.org/en/hate-speech/understanding-hate-speech/what-is-hate-speech>

⁴ *Jersild v. Denmark*. - URL: <https://globalfreedomofexpression.columbia.edu/cases/jersild-v-denmark/>

⁵ *Erbakan v. Turkey*. - URL: <https://globalfreedomofexpression.columbia.edu/laws/ecthr-erbakan-v-turkey-no-5940500-07062006/>

incite violence and where there is a real possibility that the violence occurs⁶. In this regard, in *Leroy v. France*⁷, the European Court of Human Rights upheld the conviction of three political activists for calling for violence against police during a demonstration. France, the European Court of Human Rights upheld the conviction of three political activists for calling for violence against the police during a demonstration. The Court held that the applicants' speech had crossed the line between acceptable criticism and incitement to violence, and their conviction was therefore justified under the protection of public order.

Another category of speech that may be restricted in order to protect public order is the dissemination of extremist propaganda. The ECtHR has recognized that the state has a legitimate interest in preventing the dissemination of such propaganda, as it may contribute to the promotion and recruitment of extremist groups.

In the difficult case of *FLAVUS and others v Russia*⁸, the Court held that the Russian authorities had violated the applicants' rights to freedom of expression by blocking their websites in order to ensure public order. As it turned out in the course of the proceedings, the authorities did not have such powers, as the requirement of sufficient legitimate grounds for imposing such restrictions had not been met.

Finally, as in the case of restricting freedom of speech to protect reputation, the Court has developed a system for assessing the necessity of restricting a right to ensure the stability of public order.

First of all, any interference must be provided for by law, which means that it must be based on a clear and accessible legal basis, taking into account the principles of democracy and the rule of law.

Furthermore, any restriction must pursue a legitimate aim, such as the protection of public order or the rights of others. The purpose must be adequate to justify and justify the interference and must be compatible with the principles of democracy and the rule of law.

Finally, any restriction must be necessary in a democratic society, which means that it must be proportionate to the aim and must not go beyond what is necessary⁹.

⁶ Protecting the right to freedom of expression under the European convention on human rights. - URL: <https://rm.coe.int/handbook-freedom-of-expression-eng/1680732814>

⁷ *Leroy v. France*. - URL: <https://base.garant.ru/12167519/>

⁸ *O flavus and others v. Russia*. - URL:

https://mmdc.ru/praktika_evropejskogo_suda/praktika_po_st10_evropejskoj_konvencii/ooo-flavus-i-drugie-protiv-rossii-ooo-flavus-and-others-v-russia/

⁹ Restricting Freedom of Expression: Standards and Principles. - URL: <http://www.law-democracy.org/wp-content/uploads/2010/07/10.03.Paper-on-Restrictions-on-FOE.pdf>

Restrictions on freedom of expression in the interests of public order have also often led to litigation before the Court of Justice of the European Union.

The case of *Glawischnig-Piesczek v Facebook Ireland Limited*¹⁰, which concerned a claim by Austrian politician Eva Glawischnig-Piesczek to have a defamatory post and accompanying comments removed from the Facebook platform which concerned a request by Austrian politician Eva Glawischnig-Piesczek to remove a defamatory post and accompanying comments about it from Facebook. Despite repeated requests from the applicant, Facebook refused to remove the post, citing its free speech policy and disagreement with the politician's interpretation of Austrian law. The case eventually reached the Court of Justice of the EU, which ruled that Facebook can be required to remove posts and comments found by national courts to be defamatory or unlawful, even if the material was originally published outside the jurisdiction of the court.

The Internet has dramatically changed the way we communicate and share information, but it has also made possible the spread of untruthful news, hate speech and other forms of harmful information. This case demonstrates the need for effective mechanisms to address the harm caused by such content, especially when it can have serious consequences for individuals and society as a whole.

This decision has significant implications for the activities of social media companies and other online platforms. It means that they must take proactive steps to monitor and regulate the material posted on their platforms and cannot simply rely on free speech as a defense against lawsuits. The spread of fake news and hate speech can have serious consequences for public order, undermining the democratic process and exacerbating social divisions.

At the same time, there are concerns that this precedent could lead to censorship and suppression of free speech. Some experts argue that it could be used to suppress reasonable criticism of politicians or other public figures, and to stifle dissent in countries with authoritarian governments. There are also concerns that the decision could be used by governments to increase control over the Internet and limit the ability of individuals to express themselves freely online.

It is important to note, however, that the decision under review does not imply giving the government or other authorities unlimited power to regulate online resources. Rather, it places the responsibility for regulating material on social media companies, who must balance the rights of individuals with the need

¹⁰ *Eva Glawischnig-Piesczek v Facebook Ireland Limited*. - URL: <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/liste.jsf?num=C-18/18>

to protect public order. This is a delicate and complex task, requiring careful consideration of how online speech can affect society as a whole.

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар рўйхати:

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